

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Phobia and homoeopathy

Dibyansh Kumar Singh Chauhan ¹ and Shishir Agarwal ^{2,*}

¹ Guide & H.O.D., Department of Forensic Medicine & Toxicology, Sri Ganganagar Homoeopathic Medical College, Hospital & Research Institute, Tantia University, Sri Ganganagar, Rajasthan, India.

² PhD (Homoeopathy) Scholar, Sri Ganganagar Homoeopathic Medical College, Hospital & Research Institute, Tantia University, Sri Ganganagar, Rajasthan, India.

International Journal of Science and Research Archive, 2025, 14(02), 870-878

Publication history: Received on 28 December 2024; revised on 04 February 2025; accepted on 07 February 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/ijrsra.2025.14.2.0386>

Abstract

A phobia is a type of anxiety condition characterized by an overwhelming and ongoing fear of a thing or circumstance. An instant anxiety reaction is triggered when the source of the fear is exposed. An uncontrollable, illogical, and persistent fear of a certain thing, circumstance, or action is called a phobia. A person may take extreme measures to avoid the source of their fear since it can be so overwhelming. A panic attack is one possible reaction. This is an abrupt, severe fear that lasts for a few minutes. When there isn't any actual threat, it occurs.

Diagnosis of Mental, Behavioural and Neuro-developmental disorders as coded in ICD 10 (F01 – F99) version 2025.

Keywords: Phobia; Fear; ICD; Mental Disorder; Anxiety; Stress; Patient; Homoeopathy

1. Introduction

A phobia ^[1] is a type of anxiety condition characterized by an overwhelming and ongoing fear of a thing or circumstance. When you experience severe or even overwhelming worry and terror in specific circumstances or when you come into contact with particular objects, you are said to have a phobia. The repercussions of phobias are more severe than those of typical fears, even though they can include the same items. In the worst situations, phobics severely restrict their life in order to prevent coming into contact with their fears ^[16, 18]. A phobia, a type of anxiety condition characterized by an unrelenting fear of a scenario, living thing, place, or object, is an illogical fear. When faced with the cause of their phobia, the individual will experience severe distress that may disrupt their regular activities and occasionally result in complete panic. Some people find it quite upsetting to even consider their phobia. When someone starts planning their entire life around avoiding the thing they are afraid of, they have developed a phobia. A simple dread is not nearly as serious as a phobia. Phobia sufferers have an overwhelming urge to avoid anything that makes them feel anxious.

1.1. Types of phobias

1.1.1. Phobias broadly have three different categories

- Agoraphobia: This phobia is characterized by an intense and illogical fear of being in situations from where escape is challenging. It could include a fear of crowds or even of moving away from home.
- Social phobias: This phobia, which is now called social anxiety disorder, is characterized by a fear of social settings where one could be embarrassed or judged ^[1, 2].
- Specific phobias: People are referring to a specific phobia when they discuss having a fear of a particular object, such as snakes, spiders, or needles.

* Corresponding author: Shishir Agarwal.

1.1.2. A list of some common phobias

- Ablutophobia: Fear of bathing
- Achluophobia: Fear of darkness
- Acrophobia: Fear of heights
- Aerophobia: Fear of flying
- Algophobia: Fear of pain
- Agoraphobia: Fear of open spaces or crowds
- Aichmophobia: Fear of needles or pointed objects
- Amaxophobia: Fear of riding in a car
- Androphobia: Fear of men
- Anemophobia: Fear of air
- Anginophobia: Fear of angina or choking
- Angrophobia: Fear of anger
- Anthrophobia: Fear of flowers
- Anthropophobia: Fear of people or society
- Aphenphosmophobia: Fear of being touched
- Arachibutyrophobia: Fear of peanut butter
- Arachnophobia: Fear of spiders
- Arithmophobia: Fear of numbers
- Astraphobia: Fear of thunder and lightning
- Astrophobia: Fear of outer space
- Ataxophobia: Fear of disorder or untidiness
- Atelophobia: Fear of imperfection
- Atychiphobia: Fear of failure
- Automatonophobia: Fear of human-like figures
- Autophobia: Fear of being alone
- Bacteriophobia: Fear of bacteria
- Barophobia: Fear of gravity
- Bathmophobia: Fear of stairs or steep slopes
- Batrachophobia: Fear of amphibians
- Belonephobia: Fear of pins and needles
- Bibliophobia: Fear of books
- Botanophobia: Fear of plants
- Cacophobia: Fear of ugliness
- Catagelophobia: Fear of being ridiculed
- Catoptrophobia: Fear of mirrors
- Chionophobia: Fear of snow
- Chrometophobia: Fear of spending money
- Chromophobia: Fear of colours
- Chronomentrophobia: Fear of clocks
- Chronophobia: Fear of time
- Cibophobia: Fear of food
- Claustrophobia: Fear of confined spaces
- Climacophobia: Fear of climbing
- Coulrophobia: Fear of clowns
- Cyberphobia: Fear of computers
- Cynophobia: Fear of dogs
- Daemonophobia: Fear of demons
- Decidophobia: Fear of making decisions
- Dendrophobia: Fear of trees
- Dentophobia: Fear of dentists
- Domatophobia: Fear of houses
- Dystychiphobia: Fear of accidents
- Ecophobia: Fear of the home
- Elurophobia: Fear of cats
- Emetophobia: Fear of vomiting

- Entomophobia: Fear of insects
- Ephebiphobia: Fear of teenagers
- Erotophobia: Fear of sex
- Equinophobia: Fear of horses
- Gamophobia: Fear of marriage
- Genophobia: Fear of knees
- Glossophobia: Fear of speaking in public
- Gynophobia: Fear of women
- Haphephobia: Fear of touch
- Heliophobia: Fear of the sun
- Hemophobia: Fear of blood
- Herpetophobia: Fear of reptiles
- Hippopotomonstrosesquipedaliophobia: Fear of long words
- Hydrophobia: Fear of water
- Hypochondria: Fear of illness
- Iatrophobia: Fear of doctors
- Insectophobia: Fear of insects
- Koinoniphobia: Fear of rooms
- Koumpounophobia: Fear of buttons
- Leukophobia: Fear of the colour white
- Lilapsophobia: Fear of tornadoes and hurricanes
- Lockiophobia: Fear of childbirth
- Mageirocophobia: Fear of cooking
- Megalophobia: Fear of large things
- Melanophobia: Fear of the colour black
- Microphobia: Fear of small things
- Mysophobia: Fear of dirt and germs
- Necrophobia: Fear of death or dead things
- Noctiphobia: Fear of the night
- Nomophobia: Fear of being without your mobile phone
- Nosocomephobia: Fear of hospitals
- Nyctophobia: Fear of the dark
- Obesophobia: Fear of gaining weight
- Octophobia: Fear of the figure 8
- Ombrophobia: Fear of rain
- Ophidiophobia: Fear of snakes
- Ornithophobia: Fear of birds
- Osmophobia: Fear of smells
- Ostraconophobia: Fear of shellfish
- Papyrophobia: Fear of paper
- Pathophobia: Fear of disease
- Pedophobia: Fear of children
- Philematophobia: Fear of kissing
- Philophobia: Fear of love
- Phobophobia: Fear of phobias
- Podophobia: Fear of feet
- Porphyrophobia: Fear of the color purple
- Pteridophobia: Fear of ferns
- Pteromerhanophobia: Fear of flying
- Pyrophobia: Fear of fire
- Samhainophobia: Fear of Halloween
- Scolionophobia: Fear of school
- Scoptophobia: Fear of being stared at
- Selenophobia: Fear of the moon
- Sociophobia: Fear of social evaluation
- Somniphobia: Fear of sleep

- Tachophobia: Fear of speed
- Technophobia: Fear of technology
- Thalassophobia: Fear of the ocean
- Trichophobia: Fear of hair
- Tonitrophobia: Fear of thunder
- Trypanophobia: Fear of needles/injections
- Trypophobia: Fear of holes
- Venustraphobia: Fear of beautiful women
- Verminophobia: Fear of germs
- Wiccaphobia: Fear of witches and witchcraft
- Xenophobia: Fear of strangers or foreigners
- Zoophobia: Fear of animals^[3]

1.2. Causation and aetiology

Although the precise causes of phobias are unknown, a number of variables most likely contribute to them. When your brain interprets dread and worry to an extreme degree, you have a phobia. In normal situations, these feelings can be beneficial and protective. According to research, phobias may develop as a result of a combination of environmental and hereditary variables. These consist of:

Genetics: A person is also more likely to develop a phobia if they have a close family member who suffers from a phobia or another anxiety illness. It's crucial to remember, though, that phobias can still strike those without family members who have the illness. Situational, blood, medical, and animal phobias are the ones that affect family members the most.

Traumatic experiences: Additionally, a fear may develop as a result of a challenging, stressful, or traumatic event. For instance, a childhood dog bite could cause a fear of dogs as an adult.

1.3. Epidemiology

In India, phobias are a significant aspect of anxiety disorders. The prevalence rate of phobias in India is estimated to be 4.2 percent, according to a meta-analysis of 13 psychiatric epidemiological studies. The National Mental Health Survey (NHMS) conducted in 2015-16 estimated that about 3.5% of the Indian population suffers from anxiety-related disorders, which translates to over 40 million individuals.^[13]

1.4. Clinical presentation

1.4.1. Panic and intense anxiety, which may include:

- Increased Precipitation
- Altered breathing like panting, gasping, etc.
- Tachycardia and Bradycardia
- Trembling and Dizziness
- Confusion and disorientation
- Nausea and vomiting
- Headache and Vertigo
- Hot flushes or chills
- A sensation of choking
- Chest pains and tightness
- Xerostomia (Dryness of mouth)
- Uneasiness
- Children may throw fits, weep, become too attached, or try to hide behind an object or a parent's legs.
- A feeling of overwhelming worry arises when one is exposed to the source of the dread.
- A sense that the source of that anxiety must be avoided at all costs
- When faced with the cause of the fear, the anxiety becomes so intense that it impairs the person's ability to operate.
- People who experience this often admit that their anxieties are illogical, unjustified, and overblown, but they still can't control their emotions.

1.5. Investigation and diagnosis

A doctor's goal when diagnosing a phobia is to ascertain whether or not an object causes unjustified anxiety. When talking to a doctor about their symptoms, people with phobias are usually not defensive and are almost always aware that they have one. This really aids in diagnosing. Nevertheless, millions of victims never talk to a doctor about their anxieties. This is regrettable because there are efficient remedies.

1.5.1. Prevention

Phobias happen unpredictably, and they can vary widely from one person to another. That's partly because fear is something that each person experiences differently. There are many lifestyle changes and stress management techniques one can use to prevent or avoid such diseases. There are certain triggers that can cause patient to experience psychological disturbances^[12, 17]. While triggers may be different for everyone, these are some of the best techniques one can use to prevent or avoid mental diseases / psychiatric diseases.

- Exercise regularly.
- Reduce stress.
- Get plenty of sleep.
- Stay away from toxic people.
- Eat well
- Maintain a healthy weight
- Manage chronic conditions.
- Reduce alcohol and drug use
- Get off nicotine
- Plan for unavoidable known triggers

1.6. Treatment and management

1.6.1. Medications

- Anti-depressants
- Anti-anxiety medications
- Anti-psychotic medications

Each type of medication that is used to treat psychiatric diseases has benefits and potential risks.

1.6.2. Psychotherapy

The most effective way to prevent and treat mental illnesses brought on by persistent fear is through psychotherapy. The sooner psychotherapy begins, the greater the results will be. Talking to a therapist might teach the patient coping mechanisms for unpleasant emotions. Sessions of group or family therapy may also be beneficial.

1.6.3. Exercise, Yoga and Meditation

Three to five days a week, spending roughly thirty minutes each day exercising and meditating will help to reduce stress. Exercise can boost the synthesis of mood-enhancing chemicals called endorphins. Daily yoga and meditation sessions lasting at least half an hour are highly beneficial from a preventative and therapeutic standpoint.

1.6.4. Abstinence from alcohol and drugs

For a brief period, the patient may feel better after drinking or abusing drugs. However, over time, these drugs will exacerbate mental illnesses and anxiety symptoms.

1.6.5. Self-care

In addition to keeping the patient physically well, personal care also maintains them mentally healthy, which is vital. This entails obtaining enough sleep, maintaining a nutritious diet, staying away from negative people, and engaging in fun activities.

1.7. Homoeopathic medicines

As per Synthesis 9.0 by Dr. Frederik Schroyens following homoeopathic medicines are indicated

- Arsenicum Album
- Psorinum
- Calcarea Carbonica
- Natrium Carbonicum
- Ignatia Amara
- Pulsatilla Pratensis
- Aurum Metallicum
- Calcarea Phosphorica
- Digitalis Purpurea
- Lycopodium Clavatum

<p>MIND</p> <p>PHOBIA (see Anxiety) (see Cares, full) (see Fear) (see Timidity - public)</p> <p>PHOTOMANIA (see Light - desire)</p> <p>PHYSICAL symptoms - alternating with . insanity (see insanity - alternating - physical) . mental symptoms (see Mental symptoms - alternating - physical)</p> <p>PICKING (see Gestures - hands - picking)</p> <p>PICTURE TAKEN, aversion to having his/her: (1) <i>Nat-m.</i></p> <p>PIETY, nocturnal: ♀ (1) <i>stram.</i> ♂ Praying ♂ Religious - foo</p> <p>PINCHING - children; in: ♂ (3) <i>cham. Cina hyos.</i></p> <p>PITIES herself: ♀ (34) <i>agar. aids. androc. anthraq. Aur-m-r. aur-s. bamb-a. cadm-i. CALC. carc. chir-fl. cich. des-ac. dream-p. eric-vg. germ-met. gink-b. granit-m. graph. hydrog. ign. lach. moni. musca-d. nat-sil. nit-ac. podo. puls. sal-t. Staph. suis-hep. sulph. tere-la. ulm-c.</i> ♂ Delusions - misfortune - inconsolable ♂ Delusions - unfortunate</p>	<p>♂ Unfortunate - pains; for the: (1) <i>bamb-a.</i> - sick; desire to show being: ♀ (1) <i>larant.</i> ♂ Feigning - sick</p> <p>PLACIDITY (see Mildness) (see Tranquillity)</p> <p>PLAINTIVE (see Complaining)</p> <p>PLANS - carrying out his plans; insists on (see Obstinate - plans) - making many plans: ♀ (24) <i>adam. anac. ang. arg-n. arizon-l. carc. Chin. Chinin-s. chir-fl. Coff. cortico. Ham. hydrog. ignis-alc. lec. nux-v. olnd. op. polys. sep. sul-ac. Sulph. tab. visc.</i> ♂ Absorbed ♂ Activity - creative ♂ Concentration - active ♂ Fancies - absorbed ♂ Fancies - exaltation ♂ Ideas - abundant ♂ Memory - active ♂ Programming - everything ♂ Theorizing . evening: ♀ (2) <i>Chin. Chinin-s.</i> ♂ Ideas - abundant - evening . night: ♀ (1) <i>CHIN.</i> ♂ Ideas - abundant - night</p>
---	---

Figure 1 Rubric as per Synthesis 9.0 by Dr. Frederik Schroyens (RADAR 10)

Phobias
This analysis contains 533 remedies and 3 symptoms.
Intensity is considered

			ars.	psor.	calc.	nat-c.	ign.	puls.	aur.	calc-p.	dig.	lyc.	caust.	iod.	sulph.	con.	graph.	kali-c.	sep.	verat.	bar-c.
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
Sum of symptoms (sort:deg)			11 34	11 34	11 30	11 30	11 29	11 29	11 27	11 27	11 27	11 27	11 26	11 26	11 26	11 23	11 23	11 23	11 23	11 23	11 22
01. MIND - FEAR	4	285	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
02. MIND - ANXIETY	4	485	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
03. MIND - CARES, full of	3	68	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■

Figure 2 Repertorial sheet as per Synthesis 9.0 by Dr. Frederik Schroyens (RADAR 10)

1.7.1. Arsenicum album

Hypochondriacal humour accompanied with worry and restlessness. Fear of being alone, of ghosts, of robbers, and of wanting to hide. He moves from place to place in despair. Sensitivity rose in general. Patient is sensitive to turmoil and chaos. It is characterized by indecision and fluctuating humour, demanding one item at a time and rejecting everything after obtaining it. [5, 7, 8] Despair, he suffers from misery and cannot sleep, especially at night. Patient is dejection, hopelessness, exhaustion, suicidal thoughts, or an overwhelming fear of dying, which is sometimes thought to be very close. All of the organs are extremely sensitive, noise, talking, and bright lights are intolerable. Patient experiences extreme indifference and apathy. There is delirium, with a lot of ideas flowing with a great deal of distress and anxiety which are constantly shifts. There is Phobia of Fears of dying, of being abandoned. There are Cold sweats and great terror. Patient believes that taking medication is pointless. Patient have Suicidal tendency. Smell and vision

hallucinations^[8, 10]. Anxiety, restlessness, and extreme distress that prevents sleep, usually in bed in the evening or when getting up in the morning, and frequently accompanied by shaking, cold sweats, chest pain, dyspnoea, and fainting episodes. Conscience-related worry, as though something had been done wrong.

1.7.2. *Psorinum*

The therapeutic field of this remedy is found in so-called psoric manifestations. Enjoys everything, works with pleasure, has a good sense of humour in the morning. Before going to bed, I get excited. Excited and irritated by everything. There is great fear and anxiety, with trembling palms and restlessness, particularly when riding in a carriage^[5, 9, 10]. Melancholy religious, she may kill herself, and then is characterized by phantasms, irritability, and lachrymation, she alternates abruptly with vivacity. Despair: the desire to die while having the greatest of intentions, fear of failing in business. Ill-humour, in the morning, and contemplate death all the time, could cry over anything. Patient is argumentative. Every moral feeling shuddered. There is Sentimental incapacity to get rid of thoughts that initially came to him in a dream. Assuming he understood what he had read, he attempted to explain it but was unable to do so. She has lost her memory, so when she looks out the window, she does not recognize the room. When you lift too much, your thoughts disappear. Patient is Desperate to recover, hopeless. Patient is Religious, melancholy, profound, and tenacious and Inclination toward suicide.

1.7.3. *Calcarea carbonica*

Fear of dying and discouragement. The least noisy fatigues are impatience, extreme excitability, and an excessive susceptibility to mental impulses. Patient has lack of humour, a tendency toward mischief, stubbornness, and a tendency to see the negative aspects of things. Apathy, indifference, and distaste for dialogue. Palpitations accompanied by anxiety. Obstinacy a little mental work results in a hot head. Patient is averse to effort or labour. Dislike of other people. Being alone is horrible. Disgust and dislike to any kind of work with lack of will. Patient has severe memory and conception impairment, along with cognitive difficulties^[4, 7, 10]. Patient has mental light-headedness. Patient has inclination to mispronounce words and make blunders when speaking. She worries that people would notice her mental uncertainty or that she may lose her understanding. Patient suffers from mental blunders and a loss of sense. Patient suffers from delirium accompanied by visions of rats, mice, murders, and fires. Patient suffers from Sadness, despair, and melancholy. Patient suffers from inclination to cry, especially for trivial matters. Patient has regret and vexation due to past transgressions. Patient suffers from anxiety and distress, heightened by fantasies or scary tales, accompanied by shivers and apprehension at night or in the twilight. Patient has excessive distress, accompanied by heart palpitations, blood ebullition, and epigastric shocks. Rest is prohibited due to anxious anxiety. Patient suffers from disposition to take alarm. Uneasy, gets worse in the evening, worries about losing logic, bad luck, and infectious illnesses. Patient has from low-spirited, disoriented, and forgetful. Patient often has Fears and easily offended or terrified. Youngsters have free will. Dejection brought on by a compromised health state, or hypochondriacal humour.

1.7.4. *Natrium carbonicum*

Mental weakness, despair, anxiety, hypersensitivity to noise, colds and weather changes are the key points. The Anxious and restless amid thunderstorms are worsened by music. Gayety has been marked^[7, 8]. There is sensitive to the presence of specific individuals. Patient is unable to think clearly and sluggish comprehension. Patient is Joyful chattiness and has Preference for singing. Sadness and disappointment, with tears and anxiety for the future are key points. Patient suffer In-quietude with spells of sorrow, especially during a storm or when engaged in cerebral work. Mind is aroused, and every event (music) creates trembling. Timidity, Isolation from people and civilization are marked. Patient is hypochondriacal humour and contempt with life. There is tendency to become alarmed. Patient is Irritable, Anger tendencies and violent outbursts. There is Difficulty coming up with and synthesizing thoughts when reading or listening. Patient makes errors in writing. There is difficult comprehension, which is unusual for somebody in good condition. There is imbecility or intellectual incapacity. Patient is Unfitness for intellectual work and concentration, which exhaust the mind.

1.7.5. *Ignatia amara*

The emotional component dominates the mind, interfering with function coordination. It is therefore one of the main treatments for hysteria. Women with sensitive, easily agitated personalities, dark complexions, soft dispositions, fast perception, and swift execution are particularly well-suited for it. Still, gravely sorrowful, with groaning, taciturn, with constant mournful thoughts. Patient has Sadness and deep sadness, accompanied by a sigh. Patient has irresolution, eager to do this now, that immediately. There is a strong propensity toward fear. There are quick changes in both physical and mental health, which are diametrically opposed. Patient has amazing inconsistencies^[5, 10]. Patients who suffer from intense mental or physical pain and are alert, anxious, apprehensive, rigid, and shaking are also made worse by coffee use. The most distinctive feature of its symptoms is their sporadic and superficial nature. There are involuntary

thoughts about unpleasant and unpleasant things, as well as melancholy and dissatisfied humour. Noise intolerance. Tearful sorrow alternates with silly joy. There is severe memory loss and love of being alone. Anguish, particularly when waking up in the morning or during night, occasionally accompanied by heart palpitations. Patient has variable mood, joking and laughing, then turning depressed and crying (hysteria). Patient suffers Erratic, reflective, brooding in private leading to sorrowful, depressing, and melancholy [6, 8, 14]. Not communicative Hopelessness of recovery. The slightest contradiction causes anger, passion, and facial redness, shyness and fear. Anger leads to silent sadness and mourning. Fear of night-time robbers. At the very least, provocation would be tears and total discouragement.

2. Conclusion

As we know that phobias are type of psychiatric chronic condition characterized by an overwhelming and ongoing fear of a thing and since we all know that homoeopathic has great potential of managing and treating such psychiatric disorders. Homoeopathy is customized for each person accordingly as per their innate mental constitution. Homoeopathy along with proper psychiatric guidance one can easily be freed from such phobic psychiatric disorders. For phobias, homoeopathy offers a positive, patient-centered approach with a focus on treating underlying problems. Even while its therapeutic potential is obvious, the lack of comprehensive scientific validation emphasizes the need for further detailed study to bridge the gap between clinical practice and evidence-based medicine. Future healthcare systems can provide complete and long-lasting remedies for people with phobias by combining homoeopathy with conventional techniques.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

References

- [1] Phobias [Cited on 2025 January 26]. Available from: <https://my.clevelandclinic.org/health/diseases/24757-phobias> (26 January 2025)
- [2] Phobias [Cited on 2025 January 26]. Available from: <https://www.hopkinsmedicine.org/health/conditions-and-diseases/phobias> (26 January 2025)
- [3] List of Phobias: Common Phobias From A to Z [Written by By Kendra Cherry February 13, 2023] [Cited on 2025 January 26]. Available from: <https://www.verywellmind.com/list-of-phobias-2795453#toc-az-list-of-some-of-the-more-common-phobias/> (26 January 2025)
- [4] Group Study in Homeopathic Materia Medica by Dr.J.D.Patil. New Delhi: B Jain Publishers (P) Ltd; 2018. (26 January 2025)
- [5] Text book of materia Medica (including Allen's keynotes – an easy explanation) by Dr.S.K.Dubey. Kolkata: Books and Allied (P) Ltd; 2008. (26 January 2025)
- [6] A Dictionary of Practical Materia Medica by J.H. Clarke. New Delhi: B Jain Publishers (P) Ltd; 2005. (26 January 2025)
- [7] Pocket Manual of Homoeopathic Materia Medica & Repertory by William Boericke. New Delhi: B Jain Publishers (P) Ltd; 1991. (27 January 2025)
- [8] Keynotes and Characteristics with Comparisions of some of the Leading Remedies of the Materia Medica with Bowel Nosodes (Eighth edition) by Dr. Henry C. Allen; New Delhi: B Jain Publishers (P) Ltd; 2018 (27 January 2025)
- [9] Lectures on Homeopathic Materia Medica by James Tyler Kent. New Delhi: B Jain Publishers (P) Ltd; 1905 (27 January 2025)
- [10] Leaders in Homoeopathic Therapeutics by Dr.Eugene Beauharis Nash. New Delhi: B Jain Publishers (P) Ltd; 1905 (27 January 2025)
- [11] 2025 ICD-10-CM Codes [Cited on 2025 January 27]. Available from: www.icd10data.com/ICD10CM/Codes (27 January 2025)

- [12] Cambridge dictionary [Cited on 2025 January 26]. Available from: www.dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/fright (26 January 2025)
- [13] FE Mental Health Series | Have you dismissed your phobias as mere fears? It's time for serious intervention [Written by Sushmita Panda July 31, 2024 15:25 IST] [Cited on 2025 January 27]. Available from: <https://www.financialexpress.com/business/healthcare-fe-mental-health-series-have-you-dismissed-your-phobias-as-mere-fears-its-time-for-serious-intervention-3569886/> (27 January 2025)
- [14] Physiological materia Medica by William H. Burt. New Delhi: B Jain Publishers (P) Ltd; 1978. (28 January 2025)
- [15] Everything You Want to Know About Depression, Written by Valencia Higuera. [Cited on 2025 January 28]. Available from: <https://www.healthline.com/health/depression> (28 January 2025)
- [16] 15 Ways to Avoid Depression, Written by Ana Gotter. [Cited on 2025 January 28]. Available from: <https://www.healthline.com/health/how-to-avoid-depression#15.-Plan-for-unavoidable-known-triggers> (28 January 2025)
- [17] Pathophysiology of mental illness: a view from the fourth ventricle, Written by Allan F. Mirsky and Connie C Duncan [Cited on 2025 January 28]. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/16213042A> (28 January 2025)
- [18] The burden of mental disorders across the states of India: the Global Burden of Disease Study 1990–2017, (India State-Level Disease Burden Initiative Mental Disorders Collaborators) [Cited on 2025 January 28]. Available from: <https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lanpsy/article/PIIS2215-0366-4/fulltext> (28 January 2025)